

Co-designing opportunities towards the development of Irish offshore wind

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Introduction

A series of semi-structured interviews was conducted as part of the EirWind project in order to explore the opportunities for and barriers to the development of offshore wind in Ireland.

A total of 15 interviews were conducted, 9 with Industry and 6 with Policy influencers. Industry interviewees were senior representatives of companies within the EirWind consortium. Policy influencer interviewees were drawn from the EirWind Expert Advisory Group, these were senior civil servants from across the departments of Housing Planning and Local Government, the Department of Communications Climate action and Environment and a representative of the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI).

The document presents a summary of these interviews without commentary or analysis. It is hoped that this approach will provide a clear and impartial snapshot of the nascent Irish offshore wind energy sector which can be used to facilitate informed discussions with key stakeholders.

Interviews were conducted from 1st May 2020 to 8th June 2020. This covers the period of government formation negotiations during the first phase of Covid-19 lockdown. All interviews were conducted remotely using video conferencing software in compliance with social distancing requirements.

The interview duration was typically 1.5 to 2 hours and was divided into 5 main sections:

- Expected level of offshore wind development in 2030 and 2040
- Options for defining offshore wind development zones
- Mapping exercise 2030
- Mapping exercise 2040
- Informal discussion

Throughout this document **Industry** comments are highlighted in blue text and comments from **Policy Influencers** are highlighted in green. Due to the semi-structured nature of these interviews, an exact script was not followed. However, a general paraphrased version of the questions asked and the descriptions given during the process are highlighted in **bold text** for the benefit of the reader.

1. Expected level of offshore wind development in 2030 and 2040

Interviewees were presented with Figure which was produced using data from EirGrid¹.

This report was released by EirGrid in October 2019 and it presented 3 credible scenarios for the decarbonisation of the Island of Ireland. The report covers all aspect of our energy consumption from how we power our cars to how we heat our homes. We have extracted values specifically for the development of offshore wind and have presented the development pathways under three scenarios. It is important to point out that we are expected to meet our 70% renewable electricity by 2030 target under both the “Modest Progress” and “Coordinated Action” scenarios with offshore wind making a greater contribution under the latter. Under the “Least Effort” scenario, we will miss our targets.

Figure 1. EirGrid Offshore Wind Scenarios

Interviewees were asked to provide their estimates for what level of offshore wind energy development they expect to be achieved in 2030 and 2040 and to discuss their reasoning.

A summary of estimations is provided below.

	Industry Interviewees		Policy Interviewees	
	2030 (GW)	2040 (GW)	2030 (GW)	2040 (GW)
	1	5	1.5	5.5
	1.9	6	2	6
	2.5	8	3.5	6
	2.5	6.1	3.5	6.1
	2.5	6	3.5	5.5
	3.5	6.1	3.5	6.1
	3.5	6		
	3.5	6.1		
	5	10		
Max:	5.0	10.0	3.5	6.1
Mean:	2.9	6.6	2.9	5.9
Min:	1.0	5.0	1.5	5.5

Table 1. Summary of industry and policy interviewee development projections.

¹ Tomorrow’s Energy Scenarios 2019 Ireland, Planning our Energy Future” EirGrid Plc, October 2019.

All Interviewees		
	2030 (GW)	2040 (GW)
	1	5
	1.5	5.5
	1.9	6
	2	6
	2.5	6
	2.5	6.1
	2.5	8
	3.5	6
	3.5	6
	3.5	6.1
	3.5	6.1
	3.5	6.1
	3.5	5.5
	3.5	6.1
	5	10
Max:	5.0	10.0
Mean:	2.9	6.3
Min:	1.0	5.0

Table 2. Summary of all interviewee development projections.

The commentary around the selection of these predicted levels of offshore wind development is summarised below:

Industry	
2030	1 GW
2040	5 GW

Industry	
2030	2.5 GW
2040	8 GW

- I think this whole sector really depends on the marine consenting framework, and the legislation that will overhaul the foreshore act.
- We are starting at a very low level, and in my view there will be steady enough progress on the east coast. Therefore a good number of these east coast projects will be operating by 2030.
- Once the supply chain and the development process are developed there will be more of an 'exponential growth' with a lot of installations happening past 2035.

Industry	
2030	1.9 GW
2040	6 GW

- A different approach is needed for grid connection rules. Under current rules, 1.9 GW by 2030 is the maximum that will be achieved. If there is innovation in the approach, higher is possible. A fair usage policy is needed.

- The opportunity is entirely dependent on route to market, be it interconnectors or electrolysis or other, and developing the south, the west and the Celtic Sea. These areas are an opportunity for floating
 - If the supergrid is there, we can be the Saudi of the EU

Industry	
2030	2.5 GW
2040	6 GW

- The projects that are currently defined and planned are likely to be ready for 2030, the relevant projects. Floating projects won't be in place by 2030.
 - Not all of the relevant projects will make it, some of these may struggle depending on judicial reviews. Therefore, I expect it to be somewhere between the modest and the coordinate action scenarios.

Industry	
2030	3.5 GW
2040	6 GW

- On the basis that one of the biggest barriers/limitations to increasing renewables capacity is grid, I would select 3.5 and 6GW for 2030 and 2040 respectively (i.e. based on the results of EirGrid Scenarios deemed feasible).

Industry	
2030	3.5 GW
2040	6.1 GW

- 2030 value is very optimistic, it is more of a target really.
- Finally, the level of planning support will be really important and could make or break the development of ORE and achieving this ambitious target.
- If currently planned Irish Sea projects get the 'go-ahead', then we can certainly meet the 3.5GW target.

Industry	
2030	3.5 GW
2040	6.1 GW

- The regulatory framework will decide, we need to be creative to achieve success. I have a positive / optimistic view about how this will develop. If we have a centralised approach, progress will be slow. Perhaps 1 GW by 2030. A decentralised approach will take us to the 3.5GW target.

Industry	
2030	5 GW
2040	10 GW

- The current government targets for onshore developments are completely implausible. 8GW onshore is impossible, the new onshore planning regulations reinforce this, maybe 4GW is realistic, and adding the 3.5GW offshore would still create a shortfall of 4GW

- Ireland could be quite ambitious for 2040 if floating is commercially viable at that stage, and if we want to develop in a renewable manner. We need to aim to get rid of all the oil tanks in people's gardens.

Policy	
2030	1.5 GW
2040	5.5 GW

- The 2030 number will depend on the consent framework and guidance manual (construction through to decommissioning) from a government responsibility. Additionally, our onshore experience tells us that where we have potential projects won't be necessarily be in areas where people tolerate it.

- Some other countries have difficulties with the effects of offshore wind farms, e.g. Denmark with the government currently battling concerns that there has been a negative effect on the environment by offshore wind farms. The onus is on the government there now, not on the developer. These concerns should best be addressed in advance. An 18-month delay now may prevent a 5-year delay later. Is thus maith leath na hoibre.

Policy	
2030	2 GW
2040	6 GW

- Based on progress and the current scene, I believe we are in the modest progress scenario. This is primarily because of the sole focus on the Irish Sea for this decade.

- Additionally, the indication that we are moving to a centralized model could affect investors confidence and stall the market. We need to ensure that we are giving very clear indications on timelines and ambitions.

- I think the coordinated action scenario for 2040 is achievable. We will see a slow start this decade, but we should focus our attention to develop the west coast for 2040 and thereby meet this 6GW target.

Policy	
2030	3.5 GW
2040	6 GW

- The relevant projects have been given the opportunity to go in under the offshore renewable energy regime of upcoming bills. So, I am quite confident that the relevant projects will deliver 3.5GW by 2030

Policy	
2030	3.5 GW
2040	6.1 GW

- The EirGrid figures were developed in the months running up to October and do not reflect the more recent ambition of government. We currently see 3.5GW a minimum target for 2030.

- Another big factor in the offshore scenarios is our ability to develop onshore. Our current targets set out to double our onshore capacity to 8GW, and it will be a real challenge to achieve these 4GW because of planning constraints and limited public acceptance on land.

- The early movers have been identified but they have a way to go and there is no guarantee that all of these projects will succeed. A plan is only as strong as its weakest link.

Policy	
2030	3.5 GW
2040	6.1 GW

- The value for 2040 is optimistic, it will likely require the development of more space efficient fixed wind, floating and / or other technologies which are not certainties.

Policy	
2030	3.5 GW
2040	5.5 GW

- I am optimistic, based on knowledge determination within the three principle policy divisions that are driving this forward (MSP, legislation & energy policy) to achieve success.

- We have enough shovel ready sites to meet our 2030 targets. There is a massive caveat, which is that judicial reviews can throw a spanner into the works.

- Fear for 2040 is that any pressure that has been on for 2030 will ease off, and we will see the curve flattening off.

-

1.1 Impact of Covid-19

Given that the EirGrid values were published in October 2019, these estimates were made without taking the Covid-19 crisis into account. Would you expect that the current situation would have an impact on these development rates?

- Yes in the case of projects which are currently finalising debt. I would expect that Covid will set current projects back by 6 months.

- Absolutely. One of the things that is being held up is the Marine Planning and Development Management (MPDM) Bill. There is no government to pass the legislation. Many people in the relevant departments have also been transferred to assist with contact tracing and other activities. At this stage, we can expect a 6 month delay because of Covid.

- Covid is essentially a competing project for the relevant government departments. There be reduced man power, a change of focus and borrowing restrictions. Potentially, we are looking at the first in a series of crises here.

- Yes, although it's too soon to assess what the full impact of the Covid-19 pandemic will be. What we can say with confidence though is that huge amounts of investment will be needed to rebuild the Irish economy as we move beyond this crisis. Low-carbon investment should guide Ireland's recovery.

- For a few years we will be slowed down.

- Ireland is quite bullish. If focus remains on the long term goals, then the economic slump following the Corona crisis could be used as an opportunity. Investment in large infrastructure projects will stabilise an economy.

- Any economic crisis that leads to reduced spending may impact on how we can progress. The Covid-19 economic crisis could delay deployment by about 2 years. Of course you can look at Covid-19 in terms of opportunity, but I am quite sceptical about

people changing their lifestyle after this crisis in terms of a renewed focus on what is best for society.

- We are currently a few months behind in terms of legislation, but not all of this can be put down to Covid-19, rather the election and the aftermath (government formation). A second wave of Covid is the big risk in terms of finance.

- I think Covid shifts people more towards renewables and self-sufficiency. I believe people realize the value of being independent from energy import. There is also an opportunity in terms of job creation, especially given that oil has taken a massive hit.

- Not really, offshore renewable energy is a medium to long-term development. Covid will not impact the drive to decarbonize. We have limited alternative sources of energy (solar, hydro, onshore wind), and the decision against nuclear, leaves offshore wind as the primary source. Exactly what impact is observed will depend on the make-up and priorities of any incoming Government, which is being formed.

- However, there is potential for Covid to be a stimulator for offshore renewable energy. Investing in large infrastructure projects could be used to alleviate the impacts of the emergency on employment and investment. There is cross government and cross-party recognition that we need to invest in renewables.

- If we can't get legislation passed in the next 24 months (to do so we need to get it in within 6 months), then we are really stretching ourselves to reach our 2030 targets. Virtual mechanism to allow the Dáil to operate is in development, but unsure if this will be in place in time.

1.2 UK development history

Now, let's look at the UK experience². What we have done here is overlay the rate of development of offshore wind in the UK from 2000 to 2020 on top of the EirGrid projections. So essentially what we see here is the previous two decades of development in the UK overlaid on the predicted future development of Offshore Wind in Ireland over the same time span. Would these UK values influence your response in terms of the expected rate of development in Ireland?

Figure 2. UK historic and Ireland predicted offshore wind development rates.

- No, floating wind is developing at pace. 3.5 GW by 2030 maybe conservative. The supply chain needs to be developed to maximise the Irish opportunity.
- No, happy with choice. The supply chain is matured now in the UK, we are closely located and so can leverage off that.
- No, my answer is a function of route to market. We don't have a market currently.
- I am a bit surprised about how much the UK overshot the coordinated action scenario. I would still stick with my 2030 estimate, but I would increase my 2040 estimate -> Interviewee increased 2040 estimate from 5 GW to 6 GW
- The first decade of offshore deployment in the UK is a source of 'national shame', the curve could have been much steeper in the first decade. The UK could have deployed a lot more pre-2020. They could have if caps had been

higher and consenting had been more pragmatic. Ireland should look at the speed of deployment and should strive to do much better.

- No, really confirms my estimates (1GW 2030 - 5GW 2040). The exponential growth in the UK was even more significant than expected for Ireland. However, their waters are more benign. We can really benefit from the established UK supply chain
- It wouldn't – it actually reinforces the point that these targets are achievable. The 2030 to 2040 development rate in the UK is most relevant due to the established supply chain.
- The market is more mature in the UK. A period of learning is needed before rapid development can be achieved. The interviewee reduced their 2030 value from 3.5 GW to 2.5 GW.

² UK data sourced from The Wind Power Database (<https://www.thewindpower.net>)

- The consenting process is not really fit for purpose. So I feel that we will follow the UK trajectory, almost flat to 2030 followed by a dramatic step change.

- Shows the mountain that we have to climb. 2030-40 will leave us with considerable challenges in terms of how we develop out of the east coast.

- The limitations in the UK were technological, which is no longer the case. Our limitations are in terms of the consenting and the grid. We need to maintain focus on updating policy, putting in place transparent processes and resourcing the system.

- We have late-comer advantage and we can learn from other experiences. Also, the international developers have learned a lot in

terms of deployment. Thus, the first decade of 'slow' growth in the UK may be condensed to a quicker learning period of 3-5 years in Ireland. The supply chain is there now and we can piggy back on that.

- No, we have massive second mover advantage, the first 10 years of the UK included a lot of tax payer money going in, the following decade was more cost-efficient with less expenditure incurred by the exchequer. The technology is cheaper and produces more energy now, therefore we start from a different base from the UK.

- No – Ireland should be able to capitalize on the UK development, hopefully avoid some of the pitfalls, attract some of the UK industry and supply chain.

3. Defining offshore wind development zones

Now, let's look at the options for defining offshore wind development zones. We looked at international best practice and, as you can imagine, there is a wide variety of approaches taken. What we have done is to divide these into two high level options for the purpose of this interview.

Figure 3. Zone definition options.

Under Option 1 single wind farm sites are identified centrally and developers are then invited to submit bids. This system was used in the UK Round 1 and Round 2 which covered all commercial offshore wind farm offerings from 2000 – 2010. Sites offered in the UK under this system had capacities of between 100 to 500 MW. This system has also been used in Belgium since 2000 to present with plans to continue using this system into the future. This system was used in the UK as it was early days in the industry, the supply chain, consenting process etc were not well established. It has been continued to be used in Belgium as their seabed area is so restricted and so the efficient use of space is the primary motivating factor.

Option 2, is a more decentralised approach whereby large potential development area are identified centrally and developers are then invited to identify their own sites within these areas and to submit their proposals. All proposals are then reviewed centrally. This approach has been described as crowd sourcing the identification of the most promising sites. This approach is being used under the England and Wales Round 4 offering which will run from 2020 to 2030 with the aim to develop between 7 and 8.5 GW of offshore wind.

Both options were described to the interviewees as above. They were then asked for their comments on how these options would fit in the Irish context. It was acknowledged that we are not starting from zero and that the relevant projects are in place. This discussion was thus more related to moving forward. Results are summarised in the Table 3.

	Option 1	Neutral	Option 2
Industry	2	2	5
Policy	2	2	2

Table 3. Summary of interviewees opinions on which zone definition methodology is most suited in the Irish context.

Comments on the Development Zone Definitions Options as described during the interview.

- The end result will be similar for both approaches. Generally agnostic as to which should be used although would learn toward Option 2 as it provides the developer with more control. Option 2 has essentially been implemented on the east coast already.

- In Holland much of the work is done centrally up to and including grid connect at the site. It is essentially 'plug and play' for the energy suppliers. This isn't really a game for developers. You need willing fools to drive things on. If development activities are left with government, it will be too slow.

- Both options work, both will deliver. Option 1 will be slower.

- Option 1 really isn't much of a runner, because of the lack of government resources, knowledge and the time it would take them to develop this. Also, we shouldn't rule out a merging of the two option, and the developer should always still confirm the suitability of areas that the government defines.

- At the end of the day, these are variations of a theme. Both ideas are procedurally thought-through. I would be concerned by a process that focuses solely on price. This is because a developer would be putting in extremely competitive prices. If margins are tight, even a minor economic shock could kill projects. If we start with Option 1, stakeholders and the grid infrastructure can be brought along.

- I'd select Option 2. By making the development zones large, it allows developers to use their experience and internal resources to assess as many deliverable alternatives as possible whilst avoiding removing potentially viable options.

- This Option 2 approach might not work out initially though, facing too much stakeholder opposition, causing panic among the fishing community, tourism and other stakeholders. Even though in reality there would only be 'small rectangles' developed in the vast Option 2 areas, it would be less acceptable.

- The East coast sites have already been identified. These approaches cannot be applied

retrospectively. The east coast sites should be considered based on their individual merits. Option 1 is resource-intensive and the Irish government may not have the finances and expertise to do this. Option 2 would be most suitable moving forward.

- Ireland should use Option 2. Option 1 will be too time consuming.

- I could see Ireland following an Option 1 approach but relying on the developer's resources to identify the sites. In essence, this is what has happened with the relevant projects.

- Known sites aside, The Option 2 approach is probably most sensible for future development of offshore renewable energy beyond those sites already being considered. In the UK the Crown Estate recognises that while it is the custodian of the seabed, they are not wind developers themselves.

- For Ireland, we will probably see both options or a combination of both options, probably moving to Option 2 over time. We need to get away from the 'buccaneering' mindset and achieve a plan-led approach, with complete transparency in the process and the expectations in order to give developers more certainty.

- My recommendation would be to collect more resource information as well as ecological information to work with an Option 1 model.

- In terms of Option 2, compared with the UK, Ireland may be in an advantageous position because the ownership of the seabed and decisions regarding consent are both matters reserved by the State and the Irish Government (whereas in the UK, England as an example, The Crown Estate owns and leases the sea bed whilst Government departments and agencies manage consents).

- A more centralised approach to defining development areas is needed. The developer led carve up of sites cannot continue, really this was for early stage development and needs reform.

- Either of these would work better than what we have at the moment (the developer-led approach). We are probably moving towards to a mix of Option 1 and 2.

4. 2030 - Mapping exercise

Interviewees were now shown a map of the EirWind study area. A participatory Geographic Information System (GIS) approach was used whereby a number of possible constraint layers for the development of offshore wind were introduced and discussed individually.

Interviewees were invited to turn these layers “On” or “Off” as they sought to achieve the goal of placing the capacity of offshore wind for 2030 which they stated in Section 1 of the interview. To do this they could use the Option 1 or Option 2 zone definition approach as described in Section 2 of the interview.

For Option 1, interviewees were provided with rectangular tiles representing the area of seabed required to develop a 500MW wind farm. The area was calculated on the average offshore utilisation rate of 5 MW/kM² which is a reasonable approximation of current and future offshore wind development densities³.

For Option 2, interviewees were provided with the ability to define larger zones by placing and resizing regular shapes or by drawing their own zones using a pen tool.

The purpose of this phase of the interview was to discuss the various data layers and to generally open a conversation relating to Marine Spatial Planning considerations. The locations where farms were actually placed was less relevant than the comments and decisions made. Key comments collected during this process are presented on a layer by layer basis.

4.1 Population and Grid

The first layer introduced is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Population density.

The faint grey line shows the extend of the EirWind study area which is loosely defined by the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) on the East, South and North along with the 200 m isobath on the West. The areas highlighted in orange are the main population areas in the Republic of Ireland. These are included for two reasons. Firstly, to identify areas where visual impact may be a greater concern. Secondly as a proxy to the grid infrastructure which is generally well aligned with the population distribution. This is with the exception of Moneypoint in the Shannon Estuary where there is considerable generation capacity and strong grid links to Dublin.

³ “Capacity densities of European Offshore Wind Farms”, Deutsche WindGuard GmbH, June 2018.

There was little comment on this layer with most interviewees accepting the logic. A detailed comment was provided by one industry interviewee.

-We don't agree with the overlap between population density and visual sensitivity and are very concerned that this idea is getting traction in Ireland. We believe that it is about the sensitivity of the receptor, which is not well represented by population density. There is no natural landscape

character guidance, and we suggested to the government that Ireland should go through a similar landscape assessment as Scotland has. Scotland's experience is not a panacea for Ireland but it can certainly give guidance

4.2 Distance from shore

The next layer to be introduced provided contours at 10 km intervals from shore as shown in Figure 5.

The purpose of this layer is to provide guidance on what may be acceptable in terms of the scale of development as a function of distance from shore. Whilst it is impossible to know what scale of development will be acceptable in Ireland, we can gain some guidance by looking to the UK and examining projects which have made it through the planning process.

Figure 5. Distance from shore contours.

These UK offshore wind developments are summarised Figure 6 which is a reproduction of the slide shown during the interviews.

Figure 6. UK offshore wind developments (Source: thewindpower.net)

This graph (Figure 6) shows the capacity of projects installed on the y-axis with distance from shore of the projects on the x-axis. As can be seen, a pseudo “line of acceptability” has emerged. If we plot Ireland’s only operating offshore wind farm, Arklow Bank, on this graph we see that it is well below this line. This resonates with research within the EirWind project where it was found that those living local to the Arklow Bank farm have an extremely positive opinion of the development. It is almost seen as being part of the community.

It should be noted that this graph is for guidance only, there are more than social acceptance factors at play here. Many of the near shore developments were constructed in the early days of the industry when turbines and farm sizes were smaller. However, this graph gives some guidance as to what could make it through the planning process. So, as we are looking to place the 500MW wind farms in the mapping exercise, we would look to be approximately 15 to 25 km from shore, around the second contour, in order to give us a good chance of making it through the planning process. This is for guidance only, in reality, we don’t know that will be acceptable in Ireland.

Comments from interviews on the distance from shore suggestion provided:

- Visual impact will be the primary consideration. The UK values shown are for smaller turbines. May not carry through.

- The difference in bathymetry to the UK (Irish waters get deeper much more quickly) will mean that 500MW windfarms will have to be closer to shore than in the UK. The UK example doesn’t completely translate to Ireland if you will.

- I’d be concerned about such a linear relationship to be taken by policy makers as ‘a way forward’.

- Based on UK experience in landscape and visibility assessments, 25-40km is an acceptable distance. However, if you do this in Ireland, you are in a trench right away. The primary viability concern for fixed developments is water depth (<60 m), and thus there will be trade off delivering this against increased visual impact.

- There is currently very little engagement from groups concerned about visibility of offshore turbines. Really there is only one group pushing for a buffer. There seems to be a relatively high level of acceptability because this is what we need to do to decarbonize. However, opinions can change dramatically once one of these farms are built. We need to be careful in terms of scale for these early projects.

- We are currently running a seascape assessment project. However, this cannot be summarised with a data layer, it is crucial to be on the ground and speak to communities and engage stakeholders, ideally with concrete project ideas and proposals.

- Looking at the UK example, ideally, we should be pushing all our windfarms of 500MW out to at least 20km. This does not necessarily translate to Ireland as we do not have the shallow waters further from shore. The North Sea is very different to Irish Waters.

- A lot of those smaller windfarms closer to shore were heavily subsidized and wouldn’t be economically viable going forward. Now we cannot really look at farms of <350 MW

- A balance needs to be found, we need to have a reasonable buffer which is related to wind farm size. However, just because people want to have an ‘unspoiled view’ on their morning walk, should Ireland forego its decarbonization targets and fail to tackle the fossil fuel energy crisis

4.3 Water depth

The next constraint for consideration is water depth. Obviously, our waters move from very shallow near the coast right out to the 200 m isobath on the West. However, you may wish to exclude some of these areas when placing your 2030 wind farms.

In the UK Round 1 to Round 4, so covering all commercial offshore offerings from 2000 to 2030, an exclusion of 60 m was applied. That is sites with waters deeper than 60 m were not considered to be economically viable for development.

Initially this value was set to 50 m for Round 4 but it was increased to 60 m following consultation with industry. Looking at the c.9,500 offshore wind turbines either operational or under construction worldwide, approximately 0.1% of these are in waters deeper than 60 m. For this exercise you can choose to apply the 60 m constraint, a 100 m constraint or a 200 m water depth constraint as defined by the EirWind study area.

Figure 7. Water depth constraints offered to interviewees for inclusion.

Figure 7 shows the exclusions for the 60 m and 100 m and selections for water depth constraint in 2030 are summarised in Table 4.

	60 m	100 m	200 m
Industry	5	2	1
Policy	6	-	-

Table 4. Summary of interviewee water depth constraint selection for 2030 developments.

Comments on water depth constraints for 2030:

60 m

- If a 50 m contour was there, I would choose that. But essentially, 60 m is a realistic constraint.

- Standard industry position, foundations deeper than that are not feasible, and as a matter of fact, we would go with 50m. The off-the-shelf bathymetry is not that accurate, so the 10 additional meters also serve as a buffer for the data.

- Expecting just fixed to be installed by 2030

- Whilst it's likely that by 2030 the majority of fixed wind projects will be developed in water depths <60m, there is a risk that by adding a depth

constraint, the process could hinder the development of future floating or novel fixed foundation prospects that may be viable in deeper waters

- Not best placed to comment on that as not sure down to what depths projects would be economically viable.

- That is where the technology is currently at. The space is there for what we need.

- That is the current economic technology.
- The sites need to be economically viable. What can we afford post Covid? If we are forced deeper, this will be more expensive, and a subsidy will be required.
- It would be counter-productive to introduce a more relaxed restriction given that 60m for 2030, this does not seem an option for industry. To hit the targets we need to be realistic.
- We need to be down-to-earth and plan these OWFs in realistic, cost efficient locations. That means we can't push depth or distance beyond what is done in other places.

- Based on the current technology, these will be fixed pile in less than 60m, north and south of the Dublin sweep.

100 m

- Considering a mix of fixed and floating installed by 2030.

- Totally understand why it has been 60m in most places so far, but now the technology is there to go further.

200 m

- Floating is cheaper at > 100 m water depth so that restriction is not needed.

4.4 Accessibility

In order to be able to install, operate, maintain and ultimately decommission your offshore wind farm you need access. If access cannot be achieved, you will have increased downtime which will impact the economic viability of your project due to reduced generation and the cost of vessels and personnel on standby. In the UK Round 1 to Round 4 sites were only considered to be economically viable if the significant wave height (Hs) was 2.5 m or less for 80% of a typical year. This essentially means that you could expect to be able to access your wind farm 80% of the time. We can apply this same constraint here, or if you wish, you can relax the constraint by increasing the Hs limit to 3 m , 3.5 m or 4m.

Images of resulting layers shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Accessibility restrictions

Selections for the accessibility constraint are summarised in Table 5.

	2.5 m	3 m	3.5 m	4 m	None
Industry	5	1	3	-	-
Policy	4	1	-	-	1

Table 5. Summary of interviewee accessibility constraint selection for 2030 developments.

A selection of comments on the selection of accessibility constraint in 2030 is provided below.

2.5 m

- The more benign, the easier to install, access and maintain turbines, aspects that impact the financial viability of projects and LCoE for the consumer.

- Based on my own consultations

- Not investigated in any detail, so happy to stick with the UK guidance of 2.5 m as it is tried and tested. The areas need to be financially viable at the end of the day.

- It would be prudent to stick with what the UK has gone with. For the west-coast I am very surprised about the level of constraint imposed by 2.5m wave height – this is the main take-home message for me from this interview.

- We need to cut to the chase and focus on the projects which are actually viable.

- This is primarily about practicalities for O&M and therefore OPEX costs, which drive the price of electricity in the end of the day.

- This is where the technology currently is. More (academic/innovation) work on this would be welcome so as to make more areas accessible for development.

- Just now, it is not commercially viable (to develop in harsher seas) and Ireland as a small player has little influence on it.

3 m

- Development of these (harsher) sites may not be viable until the 30's, but we need to start planning now.

- Predictions suggest that climate change will result in large waves becoming larger still and occurring more frequently. It is important that we address this wave issue in the design phase, in order to 'climate-proof' developments.

3.5 m

- Industry Interviewee was unfamiliar with this constraint but based selection on knowledge of areas which are currently being considered for development.

- We believe that we can create something serviceable in these conditions for fixed foundations. This is not really my area but I know that we are being optimistic so let's go with 3.5 m.

- This is a matter of cost, it is up to the developer to decide if the project is viable. Flotels and helicopters can be used in harsh conditions. Of course these will add to the cost. Safety is the first consideration on any project.

None - No accessibility constraint

- No really strong views – leave this constraint off for lack of expertise.

4.5 Environmental – Aquaculture

The next set of limitations relates to environmental considerations. Firstly, Aquaculture sites. As you can see these are mostly costal and represent communities involved in the production of fish and shellfish. It is important to point out that cable land fall is outside of the remit of this study.

Figure 9. Aquaculture sites (highlighted in Green)

Selections for the aquaculture layer are summarised in Table 6. “On” indicates that the interviewee opted to keep this layer active when deciding where to place their wind farms in 2030.

	On	Off
Industry	7	2
Policy	4	2

Table 6. Summary of interviewee aquaculture constraint selection for 2030 developments.

Comments summarised below

Aquaculture On

- Landfall is an important consideration that is unfortunately not sufficiently addressed.
- Cabling (distance to shore) and landfall are huge considerations for project viability.

Aquaculture Off

- The aquaculture sites are irrelevant in this process as they will not be impacted.
- Irrelevant as primarily on the west coast and therefore not where we are focusing our offshore wind farm efforts.

- I would not include aquaculture. It is quite possible that aquaculture could collocate with offshore renewable energy. Just because there is a licence / permission in a particular area does not necessarily mean that there is activity. Discussions need to be had locally – it is likely that the majority of aquaculture sites will be inshore and some distance from ORE sites (though there may be some overlap with supporting infrastructure such as cables).

4.6 Environmental – Special Areas of Conservation (SAC)

Next we have Special Areas of Conservation (SAC). These are defined under the Habitat’s Directive and whilst they do not exclude the possibility of development, an extra layer of environmental impact assessment required.

Figure 10. Special Areas of Conservation layer

Selections for the SAC layer are summarised in Table 7. “On” indicates that the interviewee opted to keep this layer active when deciding where to place their wind farms in 2030.

	On	Off
Industry	9	-
Policy	5	1

Table 7. Summary of interviewee SAC constraint selection for 2030 developments.

Comments on the SAC layer are summarised below:

SAC On

- I don’t think that anyone is rushing to build an offshore wind farm in an SAC.
- We generally wouldn’t consider developments in areas that are SACs, also because they are closer to shore (< 10 km) than what we would consider viable.
- Our initial experience from onshore wind was that getting planning permission in/near SACs was possible but that has become increasingly difficult. So now, we include these as a constraint in our scoping for new sites.
- Spatial-temporal & species need to be considered when it comes to SACs. Also, management and enforcement needs to happen,

paired with some level of monitoring that assesses whether the protection targets have been met. Co-existence is possible.

- I would suggest that we try to be pragmatic and limit it to the ones that represent a direct conflict of interests with OFWs.
- There are more SACs to come, and this is important to include over the years to come

SAC Off

- With SACs, it depends on what they are designated for. If they are designated for species/habitats that are not adversely affected by windfarm development, the questions should be asked as to whether or not colocation is possible.

4.7 Environmental – EPA Dumping Grounds

These are areas where dredge material, primarily from ports and quays, is dumped at sea. Whilst there is no engineering reason why wind farms cannot be developed in these areas, there is a convention to exclude areas for consideration when there is an existing licenced activity.

Figure 11. EPA dumping zones layer.

Selections of the EPA layer are summarised in Table 8. “On” indicates that the interviewee opted to keep this layer active when deciding where to place their wind farms in 2030.

	On	Off
Industry	7	2
Policy	4	2

Table 8. Summary of interviewee EPA dumping ground constraint selection for 2030 developments.

Comments on the EPA layer are summarised below:

EPA On

- Concern with dumping sites is mostly consentability in Ireland, which might be hampered because of existing activities
- Wouldn't completely rule out EPA dumping grounds for all development, but leave them in to consider them. See them as more of a soft constraint.
- We'd be concerned about previous levels of disturbance and a potential to create a pollution incident.
- Should be included in assessment methodology to define zones in line with SEA undertaken for OREDP.
- If EPA weren't completely exclusive, I'd see some opportunity, but it seems to add complexity.

4.8 Infrastructure

The next layers to be introduced related to offshore infrastructure, namely: gas lines, interconnectors and licenced activities for oil and gas. A 500 m buffer was applied to lines. The oil and gas licenced areas are located at Kinsale Head and Corrib.

All infrastructure layers are shown in Figure 12. At the time of the interviews, the landfall of the Celtic interconnector had not been finalised as so this terminates approx. 20 km from the Southern Coast.

Most interviewees kept these infrastructure layers "On" when placing their 2030 wind farms. This is with the exception of one industry interviewee that turned Oil + Gas areas "Off" and one industry interviewee that turned pipeline and interconnectors "Off. All six policy interviewees kept these 3 layers "On".

- The concern with EPA grounds would be the disturbance of contaminants.

EPA Off

- EPAs relevant but not sure if leaving in as a general exclusion, possibly more of a project level decision. Dispersion of sediment is the main concern here.
- Not certain of the state of these sites but there may actually be an advantage to developing on these sites because of potentially lower biodiversity and consequently lower levels of fishing activity. Again, just because there is a licence does not mean that there is activity so this would need to be looked into. Given the pace of change required, these site may have to be considered.

Figure 12. Infrastructure restriction layers. Interconnectors area shown in red with gas pipelines in black.

A summary of comments on the infrastructure layers is provided below:

All layers on

- If there is an exploration for oil and gas ban the oil and gas zones should be fine. But it is a mute point to 2030 given the availability of less challenging sites.
- Absolutely to all, Oil and Gas is just for completeness. These sites (e.g. Kinsale and Corrib) are not relevant out to 2030.
- These should all be included in assessment methodology to define zones in line with SEA undertaken for OREDP.
- Normal corridor approach (for pipeline and cables) needs to be maintained.

- Old oil and gas sites would be potential sites in to the future but not before 2030.

Licensed activity layer Off

- I see no reason to exclude Kinsale O+G areas because it's mostly exploration licenses. We need clear guidance on the pipeline buffer. Will it be 500 m in Ireland? Clear guidelines for oil and gas exploration areas are lacking in Ireland. We need to have an open discussion around reuse / repurposing.

Pipeline and interconnectors Off

- Need to adjust (wind farm) configuration to pipelines. They should not be excluded.

4.9 Fishing

The next layer is to do with fishing activities. What we have done here it to examine AIS data and have extracted data relating only to fishing vessels. Using these data, we have identified the top 10% and top 20% busiest areas in terms of fishing activity.

Note: During the interview process Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) data became publicly available. This dataset provides a significantly higher level of detail relating to fishing activities. These data are being processed and will be included in EirWind GIS outputs.

Figure 13. Fishing activity layer.

A summary of fishing constraint layer selections are provided in Table 9.

	None	10%	20%
Industry	2	2	5
Policy	3	-	3

Table 9. Summary of interviewee fishing activity constraint selection for 2030 developments.

None - No fishing data included

- Fishing is not a simple on/off. Pot based fishing will be fine. Trawling will be a problem. There needs to be a project level case by case assessment based on community engagement and the type of activity.

- Fishing community is the most invested in the marine environment. We need to come up with a way for the two industries to cohabitate. This depends on the vessel being used, with smaller vessel incurring a greater impact because of lower range compared to bigger vessels. We would consider the data, but we would not consider this an exclusion criterion, just to flag the potential added project complexity.

- A lot of these data exclude the smaller vessels (<10m). This is up to 80% of the vessels involved. It is important that this community are engaged with. It is mostly fixed gear fishing within <12nm. Generally, zoning fishing cannot be accomplished as it varies with the type of activity and the season etc. The limit for fisheries are quotas, they are not limited by zone.

- Use of such maps should not be discouraged but they must be used in the right way and include relevant representation of activity – what narrative do maps provide / stories do they allow you to tell? For example, in the maps shown there is a difficulty in relation to a lack of data for small scale fishing. The communities have a far greater connection to these smaller vessels.

- Maps of this kind are useful to start the conversation, but consultation is necessary. This is difficult as the areas which are fished is commercially sensitive information. However, I have been very encouraged with the level of engagement from the fishing community in the draft National Marine Planning Framework (NMPF).

- As with everything occurring at sea, safety of life is the primary concern and top priority. One of the biggest concerns with interarray fishing, aside from the obvious risk of collision, is the means of rescue if something went wrong given access is limited and challenging where it is possible.

10% Fishing Activity

- Good to have this in for guidance but we need to talk to the fishers on a project by project basis.

- Good to use the top 10%. Very aware that there is a need to bring the fishing communities onboard through the consultation process.

20% Fishing Activity

- Further data and stakeholder engagement is needed. Important to note that fishing areas may shift over time.

- Fishing is a huge issue. Developers need to work with fishers delicately. It will take significant effort to find pathways to work with fishermen. All areas of fishing interest need to be included. Depending on the type of fishing activity, different approaches will be required.

- Particularly for starting a new sector, especially on the West, it seems prudent to go with the 20%.

- The NMPF and guidelines developed in other jurisdictions (such as the FLOWW best practice guidance) should be considered in order to facilitate coexistence.

- We need to have respect for fishermen. Fishing activities will have to cease during construction but once the farm is operational an increase in fish stocks can be seen. Fishing can be allowed within the farm with compensation paid during construction. Fishing will be a big problem if it is not considered.

- Fishing is the biggest challenge to new marine activities. This is particularly true to countries where fishing has a clear constituency.

- I believe this will be very important, and we will have to re-create the structure from the UK with a strong liaison between ORE and the fishing industry.

- Sectoral agreements in other EU-member state such as in the Netherlands can be a guidance on how to deal with conflicts between ORE and other users/no-users.

4.10 Shipping – Traffic Separation Schemes

The next set of layers are to do with shipping. Firstly, the Traffic Separation Schemes (TSS). These are defined by the International Maritime Office (IMO) and are policed locally by the Coast Guard. As you can see, there is a large TSS off the coast of Wexford and another off the Coast of Kerry. These act effectively as lanes on the motorway and there is strict adherence to these by larger vessels. Between the TSS and the ports vessel movements diverge as they are provided with freedom of navigation.

Figure 14. Traffic Separation Scheme layer.

Summary of selections of the TSS constraint layer is provided in Table 10.

	On	Off
Industry	9	-
Policy	6	-

Table 10. Summary of interviewee TSS constraint selection for 2030 developments.

Comments on the Traffic Separation Scheme constraint:

TSS On

- With TSSs, it's not a question of 'wanting' to include them, you simply have to. This could have implications in the high court years down the line.
- Leave TSS on because they are problematic for development

- TSS and shipping lanes are in place to ensure safety of life at sea and should be considered as hard constraints.
- These could be adjusted in the future if needed.
- IMO TSSs are a hard constraint – these are important to the Irish economy but also to the safety of life at sea. These were put where they are for a reason, it would take years to move them.

4.11 Shipping – Shipping lanes

Whilst these are not policed in the same manner at the TSS, they are defined in the admiralty charts. What you see when looking at vessel density data is that traffic tends to converge on these lanes approx. 5 to 10 kM from shore, but beyond that, they are taken as more of a guidance.

Figure 15. Shipping lanes layer.

A summary of selections of shipping lane constraint layer is provided in Table 11

	On	Off
Industry	6	3
Policy	5	1

Table 11. Summary of interviewee shipping lane constraint selection for 2030 developments.

A summary of comments on the shipping lane constraint layer is provided below.

Shipping lanes On

- Lanes included more for information.
- As for lanes, experience with the UK is that they are very difficult to get moved, even though in some cases this has been done and could hopefully be done in places of the Irish EEZ. For this exercise, they should be in.
- With lanes, we take the view that these are not very well adhered to. However, they are a significant barrier to development, which we would look at with government on an individual-development basis.

- Nobody thinks that lanes are important until you ignore them, and then you get a push back from, the sector. I would leave them on for scoping.
- Lanes, let's keep them in for information.
- It is easier to move lanes than IMO TSSs, but still very important to be mindful of.

Shipping lanes Off

- Looking at lanes as a guidance, I wouldn't include it as a restriction in this exercise.

4.12 Shipping – Vessel Density

The final layer that we have in the shipping section is vessel density which is derived from Automatic Identification System (AIS) data. When we map all AIS data, we see that there are essentially vessels going everywhere in the EirWind study zone. What we have done to express this in a meaningful way is the extract data only for tankers and cargo vessels for the past 12 months. From this, we selected the top 1-1.5% busiest areas in terms of vessel density within our study zone.

Figure 16. Vessel density layer.

A summary of selection of the vessel density constraint layer is provided in Table 12

	On	Off
Industry	6	3
Policy	4	2

Table 12. Summary of interviewee vessel density selection for 2030 developments.

A summary of the commentary on the vessel density layer is provide below:

Vessel Density On

- These clearly need to be taken into account.
- We do agree with using AIS density data.
- Shipping density can be assessed at (both) strategic and project level through AIS and VMS data.
- Leave density on for 2030, though I would presume that ships would move if a wind-farm was built, especially as those density maps have no legal basis.

- (Density – included but these elements really take shape at project level

Vessel Density Off

- Excluding shipping density as these routes are reactive not proactive.

- With the density data, glad to see it and keep it as a soft constraint, but not as a hard constraint

- Vessel density is interesting but it is a project level decision

- Vessel density does not need to be included – vessels have the freedom of navigation in waters as they seem fit. However, the economic impact of rerouting necessary to avoid ORE should be properly considered with input from industry and Government. Passenger vessel margins in particular can be sensitive to lengthening of routes.

- It is important to differentiate between vessels that have no Irish contact, those that start or stop in Ireland and those that start and stop in Ireland. The economic value to Ireland and the relationship the

different routes have with coastal communities varies substantially for these three groups.

4.13 Output of constraint layers 2030

As can be seen from the sections above, there was broad consensus among the two cohorts with regards the layers that should be included when locating wind farms which are expected to be operational by 2030. Compiling data from all interviewees and taking the most popular selection for each category is summarised in Table 13.

Layer	Selection	% selecting
Water depth	60 m	75
Accessibility	2.5 m	56
Aquaculture	On	69
SAC	On	88
EPA Dumping	On	69
Oil and Gas	On	94
Pipeline & Interconnectors	On	94
Fishing	20%	50
TSS	On	94
Shipping lanes	On	69
Vessel Density	On	63

Table 13. Summary of interviewee constraint selections for 2030 developments.

The result of mapping the most popular interviewee selections is shown in Figure along with a set of purple rectangles each representing the area required to develop a 500 MW wind farm. A total of 3.5 GW is shown, this corresponds with the anticipated level of development of offshore wind as set out in the Climate Action Plan⁴.

The white areas close to the coast are the areas in which no constraints were identified during this exercise.

Figure 17. Average constraint selections for 2030.

⁴ “Climate Action Plan 2019”, Department of Communications Climate Action & Environment, Government of Ireland, August 2019.

Interviewees were now asked to place their 2030 wind farms using either the Option 1 or Option 2 approach as summarised in Section 2. Table 14 summarises selections

	Option 1	Option 2	Both
Industry	8	1	-
Policy	4	1	1
Total:	12	2	1

Table 14. Summary of interviewee usage of Development Zone Definition Option usage when placing 2030 developments.

As can be seen, there was a strong preference among both groups for the use of the more centralised Option 1 Zone Definition approach when placing the 2030 farms. However, this choice was heavily influenced by prior knowledge of the location and existence of the relevant project on the East Coast.

The most selected locations for the placement of the Option 1 and Option 2 zones are shown in Figure 18 for the Industry and Policy groups. A simple overlay approach is used whereby if an area is selected more than once its rank is increased. A min-max stretch was applied in order that zones selected by both groups could be compared. Due to the crude nature of the online interface used and the hypothetical nature of this mapping exercise, the images in Figure 18 should be considered indicative only.

The overlap of areas selected by interviewees as development zones for 2030 and the potential GW capacity which these areas represent are summarised in Table 15. A development rate of 5 MW per KM² is used⁵ and the full development of the selected area is assumed in all cases.

		Overlap area (km ²)	Potential capacity (GW)
Number of interviewees selecting area	2	5404	27.0
	3	1973	9.9
	4	543	2.7
	5	265	1.3
	6	180	0.9
	7	156	0.8
	8	150	0.8
	9	120	0.6
	10	66	0.3
	11	42	0.2
	12	26	0.1
	13	1	6.5 (MW)
	14	0	0.2 (MW)

Table 15. Summary of the overlap of interviewee development zone selections 2030.

⁵ “Capacity densities of European Offshore Wind Farms”, Deutsche WindGuard GmbH, June 2018.

Figure 18. Development zone selection results 2030. **Note:** This was a hypothetical exercise, zones shown are indicative only.

4.14 Additional layers

The final stage of the 2030 mapping exercise was to ask interviewees if there were any data layers which they felt should have been included in this process in addition to those considered. Responses as follows:

- Should also consider: grid connection, windspeed, ports, mammals, birds.
- Seabed conditions are very important for jack-Up vessels and the other consideration is that the seabed moves (stability) and you need to bury your cable). We don't want to be building on a mountain ridge.
- Grid connection points / infrastructure need to be included in this process.
- Really, we are missing grid & seabed data. This would be a real challenge for the Wexford development.
- Ornithology is key filter that is missing in this process, SBA (special Bird areas), mammal foraging data are a very important consideration for development and de-risking. Along with sensitive iconic landscapes (Cliffs of Moher), UNESCO sites etc that are important for tourism.
- Seabed condition, bathymetry and soil type.
- There's got to be a 'crystal-ball gazing' layer of what you expect the seascape and its uses to be like between 2020-2040. The picking an appropriate timescale is crucial when we do such a mapping exercise. Future MPAs with a potential increase in the policy target to 30% by 2030. Currently we are at 2%.
- SPAs are a big omission here and need to be included. The barrier effect when a lot of farms are built in an area will be an important consideration.
- Proper VMS data will also change certain elements, especially with major nephrops fishing grounds in the very South and in the North-East.
- Information is required on birds and marine mammals.
- Fáilte Ireland designated coastal areas of beauty should be included in this.
- Existing wind farms and their cables.
- Communications lines. With e-commerce and banking this is an area of growth.
- Military practice zones, particularly those designated as "Danger Areas".
- Existing ORE test sites.
- Recreational sailing is important in some areas, but this would be a project level decision.

5. Mapping exercise - 2040

In this phase of the interview attention turned to placing the interviewee’s wind farms in order to achieve their 2040 development expectations. Again, a set of 500 MW wind farms to the required capacity were supplied and interviewees were asked to identify development zones using either the Option 1 or Option 2 method as defined in Section 3. Before embarking on this exercise, the active data layers from the 2030 mapping exercise were reviewed and the interviewee was invited to make any changes necessary to reflect the passage of time and advancement of technologies.

There were no significant changes to most layers with the exception of Water Depth and Accessibility. The changes are summarised below.

5.1 Water Depth - 2040

Most interviewees chose to increase the maximum considered water depth when placing their 2040 farms. A summary of changes is presented in Table 16.

	60 m to 100m	60 m to 200 m	100 m to 200 m
Industry	3	3	1
Policy	3	3	-

Table 16. Summary of interviewee water depth constraint modifications for 2040 developments.

Following these reviews, the water depth criteria selection for 2040 is summarised in Table 17.

	60 m	100 m	200 m
Industry	-	4	5
Policy	-	3	3
Total:	-	7	8

Table 17. Summary of interviewee water depth constraint selection for 2040 developments.

Comments for changes implemented to water depth are summarised below:

60 m to 100 m

- Wouldn’t go beyond 100 m for the next round of development
- Most of the potential on the west coast will be delivered through floating offshore wind farms, not sure if there will be any opportunity for fixed on the South or West.
- Increase as floating might be commercial by then
- At this stage floating should be more economically viable.
- All dependent on how technology is moving forward
- Floating technologies should be considered at this stage.

60 m to 200 m

- Post 2030 floating will be viable – no restriction at that point
- By 2040 there will likely be fixed up to 70/80 m and floating over 100 m. Expect a development dead zone between 80 to 100m
- Setting a depth limit to define a development zone may rule out viable projects.
- Certainly, a level above 100m with floating coming about
- We have to assume that by 2035, depth and wave won’t matter too much anymore.

100 m to 200 m

- 200 m as a constraint will be fine for 2040.

5.2 Accessibility - 2040

Most interviewees also chose to increase the maximum wave height at which offshore wind farms can be accessed when placing their 2040 farms. A summary of changes is presented in Table 18.

	2.5 m to 3 m	3 m to 3.5 m	3 m to 4 m	3.5 m to 4 m	2.5 m to None
Industry	3	1	-	1	1
Policy	2	-	1	-	1

Table 18. Summary of interviewee accessibility constraint modifications for 2040 developments.

Following these reviews, the accessibility criteria selection for 2040 is summarised in Table 19.

	2.5 m	3 m	3.5 m	4 m	None
Industry	1	3	3	1	1
Policy	1	2	-	1	2
Total	2	5	3	2	3

Table 19. Summary of interviewee accessibility constraint selection for 2040 developments.

Comments for changes implemented to accessibility constraint are summarised below:

2.5 to 3

- The situation will certainly be better with more sites viable. Hard to say how much better the situation will be.

- The technology will have matured

- Difficult one, Health and Safety considerations need to be paramount especially for early floating projects.

- This, however, brings back pressure to develop sites on the east coast which have opened (as a result of relaxing this constraint).

- We have to expect advancing technologies.

- This will be a function of developments in the technology and will be a key consideration in the definition of any zones.

3 to 3.5

- Drones might fly out to do much of the O&M, and our engineering will have solved some of the difficulties with access to turbines.

2.5 to none

- Limiting the limits may in turn limit innovation

- We have to assume that by 2035, depth and wave won't matter too much anymore.

5.3 Output of constraint layers 2040

There was again broad consensus among the two cohorts with regards the layers that should be included when locating wind farms which are expected to be operational by 2040. Compiled data from all interviewees and the most popular selection for each category are provided in Table 20.

Layer	Selection	% selecting
Water depth	None	53
Accessibility	3 m	33%
Aquaculture	On	69
SAC	On	88
EPA Dumping	On	69
Oil and Gas	On	94
Pipeline & Interconnectors	On	94
Fishing	20%	50
TSS	On	94
Shipping lanes	On	69
Vessel Density	On	63

Table 20. Summary of interviewee constraint selections for 2040 developments.

Mapping the most selected setting the resulting map is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Average constraint selections for 2040.

Interviewees were now asked to place their 2040 wind farms using either the Option 1 or Option 2 approach as described in Section 2. Table 21 summarises which options were used in 2040.

	Option 1	Option 2	Both
Industry	2	6	1
Policy	-	6	-
Total:	2	12	1

Table 21. Summary of interviewee usage of Development Zone Definition Option usage when placing 2040 developments

As can be seen, there was a strong preference among both groups for the use of the more decentralised Option 2 Zone Definition Approach for the 2040 farms. This is in stark contrast to the 2030 scenario when Option 1 was preferred by 12 of the 15 respondents. To some extent, this choice was influenced by the distinct and uncertain nature of these 2040 developments which led the interviewees to select the Development Zone Definition Option which was less prescriptive.

The most selected locations for the placement of the Option 1 and Option 2 zones in 2040 is shown in Figure for the Industry and Policy groups. Again, a simple overlay approach is used whereby if an area is selected more than once its rank is increased. A min-max stretch was applied in order that zones selected by both groups could be compared. Due to the crude nature of the interface used and the hypothetical nature of this mapping exercise, the images in Figure 20 should be considered indicative only.

The overlap of areas selected by interviewees as development zones for 2040 and the potential GW capacity which these areas represent are summarised in Table 22. A development rate of 5 MW per KM² is used⁶ and the full development of the selected area is assumed in all cases.

		Overlap area (km ²)	Potential capacity (GW)
Number of interviewees selecting area	2	87313	139.4
	3	27872	66.6
	4	13313	21.0
	5	4202	11.7
	6	2332	12.2
	7	2447	7.4
	8	1478	4.6
	9	921	3.4
	10	684	1.7
	11	343	0.8
	12	163	0.2
	13	37	6.48 (MW)
	14	1	0.15 (MW)

Table 22. Summary of the overlap of interviewee development zone selections 2040.

⁶ “Capacity densities of European Offshore Wind Farms”, Deutsche WindGuard GmbH, June 2018.

Figure 20. Development zone selection results 2040. **Note:** This was a hypothetical exercise, zones shown are indicative only.

6. Informal discussion

The final stage of the interview was an informal discussion to capture any points which were missed during the interview. A semi-structured interview approach was again used with four questions to frame the discussions. Specific responses to these questions are provided below.

6.1 What is the purpose of Offshore Wind Development Zones?

The aim of this question was to gain a broad sense of the interviewee's perspective.

- To optimise the installation and operation of offshore wind farms by considering existing and future users.
- To maximise offshore wind development in a systematic and reasonable way.
- To provide clarity of ambition and to allow developers to evaluate risk.
- They should be a guide to where offshore wind farms would be acceptable/permittable, subject to further investigation by the developer. This should help the developer to avoid spending millions on a project that then cannot be developed.
- We shouldn't forget that achieving our goals will require massive private investment, so identifying the most valuable zones and offering them to the market is really important. This will reduce/mitigate risks for investors. Otherwise investors will just go to other jurisdictions.
- Ensuring that everyone's interests in the marine environment and that the opportunities for the state are maximized in terms of capacity and cost.
- The areas identified should help to reduce development risk and facilitate coexistence.
- To ensure that the maritime space is divided between different sea users and the environment is protected.
- To focus areas for OWF development and to allow developers to scope projects and reduce conflict with other users.
- They bring certainty to everyone involved in the process about: Where, When, How Much, Who will benefit? Who will carry the risk?
- They are to clearly delineate the area of activity for offshore wind, so that everyone is aware the nature and extent of the activity.
- To streamline policy decisions and infrastructure developments, particularly grid and ports.
- The best way of ensuring a return to the state to meet domestic requirements and to maximise social acceptance.
- To bring certainty, create efficiency and fast-track decarbonization.
- To provide certainty to all actors

6.2 What should be provided in addition to coordinates on a map?

This question related to how much information, support, infrastructure should be provided centrally when offshore wind development zones are defined and offered to developers.

- Visual impact and fishing are the main points. A robust central analysis needs to be provided.

- An agreed set of constraints is needed. There will always be some restrictions within the sites (e.g. cable routes, ship wrecks, well heads) as per the UK sites. But we need to know what and where these are. These constraints need to be decided and all available data provided and then leave the decision to the developer if they feel they can economically find a solution. For example, a threshold shipping density should be provided, not as a hard development exclusion, but for the developer to decide if they can make it work.

- Projects need to be developer led or this will be too slow. The government just need to make these zones big enough and to give guidance on consenting process.

- Assistance in coordinating grid access, but this is unlikely to happen beforehand and may need to be done in parallel with the site development.

- Grid, assistance with stakeholder engagement and supporting to bring everyone onboard, mediating conflicts between ORE developers and the fishing community. It's important that these moderating efforts are not influenced by individual constituency demands.

- Environmental issues should be the state's responsibility to define acceptability but, while the developer should assess the technical feasibility and demonstrate the environmental credibility of the scheme.

- If future zones selected are based on best scientific data, the principles outlined in the NMPF, the OREDP and consultation with stakeholders, all

the information behind delineating these areas should be provided centrally in addition to coordinates on a map.

- Seabed conditions (if available) as well as methodology by which these zones have been selected.

- Coordinates are fine for now. Ireland needs to get started and to start with big farms.

- As much information and guidance as possible – what is expected if you are carrying out this activity? The information must fulfil a certain standard, including setting out level playing-field conditions for all actors.

- A large element of this should be provided centrally. The base case for a development should be made & coordinated centrally and provided to all interested parties. This could and should include basic environmental data but potentially also some on other maritime activities.

- Grid connection should be provided, but we cannot wait for this to be done before kick-starting the OWF development process.

- Policy question that is being worked on. A grid connection policy is crucial and is currently in the works.

- Option 1, more specific, should come with a full suite of project plans including the provision of a grid connection. In terms of the less hands-on Option 2 approach, coordinates would be fine. Along with a guarantee regarding competing interests from other potential users. Grid will be the main driver for these

6.3 Main skills shortages, if any, to enable the development of offshore wind in Ireland?

The responses to this question were divided among two broad areas, skill shortages in industry and skill shortages in the relevant government departments. Comments relating to these two areas will be provided separately.

Industry shortages

- Operational offshore wind experience.
- Really there are not many, we have a strong development community who will make this happen, they have done much of the early work already. Really the construction expertise and supply chain will come from other regions. These are mobile resources. Fishing can pivot to contractor roles if required.
- Most of the required skills are available in the UK. We need to ramp up our own training particularly in O+M. This needs to be conducted along side port infrastructure development. Building the actual platforms is not the opportunity, there may be some jobs in assembly. The real opportunity is in other areas like technology and IT to enable the transformation of electricity into a vector.
- Our ports are not ready for this. Access equipment, including their construction and maintenance is lacking.
- There is no offshore wind industry in Ireland, and also a general lack in marine engineering, even though there is a bit of a maritime (shipping) sector. In the short term, a lot of these gaps in the supply chains will be filled internationally, but in the long run you would expect that this industry will develop in Ireland.
- There are huge skill gaps currently in the construction sector. Similarly, there will be massive skill shortage in the heavy engineering, welding, the whole supply-chain really.
- There is a global shortage of skilled people to enable the sector to reach its potential. It seems that there is about a 20-25% shortage in labour globally and I'd suggest a higher shortfall in Ireland.
- There is a shortage of vessels, electrical engineers, mechanical and civil engineers with experience in the marine sector. There is significant competition from other countries and other sectors.

While there are transferable skills from the O&G sector, the pay is not at the same level and therefore the workforce isn't currently lured over from fossil to renewable energy companies.

- Most people are working on the assumption that the engineering and construction skills that have been developed/trained in the UK will be made available here. As the industry gets going and we build momentum, these jobs can eventually come to Ireland
- Turbine and offshore experience. Workers can be trained by the industry if the scale of the opportunity is large enough. Installation, cable laying and other vessels are mobile, however, they need to be facilitated by infrastructure.
- It's important to get the message across to politics & policy makers that there is a considerable opportunity, but that some of the optimism on supply chain seems misplaced or if it is to be realised needs to be delivered with the support of significant intervention. We can seize upon this, but only if the policy and consenting framework dove tail together.
- Heavy engineering competency that needs to be created nationally. In the short term, these skills will be imported.
- Really there are shortages across the supply chain and these need to be developed. These skills will come from international suppliers, we can't set an Irish limit of input for near term projects. It will make them non-viable.
- Skills will follow the industry. Currently, there is no Irish port which will be able to facilitate offshore wind farms in terms of deployment. We are better placed for maintenance ports, because crew transfer vessels are smaller.
- Good, high-paying jobs will attract the right people. These won't be huge numbers, but if placed in rural ports, 50-70 good, high paying jobs can be a

game changer in terms of regional development opportunity. Many Irish are working in this sector internationally and may take this opportunity to come home

- Many of our neighbours are competing for the same skill sets for their own offshore wind developments. And often this is with a stronger and less uncertain pipeline of projects.

Government shortages

- Government departments need better resourcing to coordinate process and stakeholders. EIA, habitat regulations, judicial review process are technically and administratively demanding

- I would have massive concerns regarding the immediate shortages in government departments for consenting.

- Plans, processes and necessary legislation is being put in place by the Government to enable development, but once this is done, all of this will need to be managed. There will be significant work to consent and deliver offshore projects. There will therefore be a requirement for skills and resources to do this and ensure that CPA targets are met.

- We have significant capacity shortages in terms of maritime governance. We are currently creating wish-lists and giving very high promises, but maybe unable to deliver at that level.

- Resources and processes are in place to ensure projects that are known to be at some stage of development (concept/early planning through to consent authorised) are developed. Given the expected pace of ORE growth in Ireland and the novel characteristics of these types of developments, these provisions will need to be kept under review to ensure the most effective support for project delivery.

- Teams in other comparable European administrations are much larger, there is a significant capacity shortage in our policy departments.

- Worried that development will be left to the free market with all these skills being shipped in from the continent. That includes everything from R+D to boots on the ground. This is a concern at the European level, with a hope/intention that the skills/knowledge will be shared across the continent rather than concentrated in one country.

- This is really a question for industry but reflecting what I have heard from stakeholders I would say surveying to inform applications, installation, fabrication, O+M.

- There are significant requirements in the government departments involved in the processes. They may be overrun with Environmental Impact Assessments and have to ensure a quick turnaround.

- We are aware of ourselves that there is a shortage, we are in the process of staffing up an energy department.

- To support this industry, we need more focus in the responsible government departments. A team of about 10 would be needed for a good 6 months (including a lawyer, a valuer) to give a project like Arklow Bank the attention that it would deserve.

- More important than skill/capacity shortage is focus. A smaller team can achieve a lot if they are focused solely on the task. I'd like to see a priority set on 'site investigation for ORE', with 4 people dedicated to that.

- There are a lot of good people across departments who are willing to help out with advice and information. This network of willing and expert helpers extends into organisations such as MaREI and the Marine Institute. There is no formal structure on this and I would be worried that it may be lost with the departure of key people and relationships.

- This is an emerging industry, training and resourcing will likely be required to ensure ongoing capacity is sufficient to review and process the expected increase in applications that will be required in order to meet the targets.

6.4 Any other comments?

- The work today touched on main key points. The consolation process should follow a similar method.

- This was a very useful exercise and a useful tool. Would be beneficial for internal use to facilitate a conversation around the opportunity.

- Amazing job in gathering all this information, and the interactive exercise was very engaging.

- Good exercise, because it certainly shows very clearly that the space is actually quite limited once all the other users, protected areas and technical constraints have been plotted on.

- It is useful what you have done. I have a curiosity about how these things have been done in the Netherlands or Denmark, rather than the UK,

because of the natural similarity (in terms of national psyche).

- This is very useful tool. It would be useful for policy makers to step through this process to inform their decisions. The data and its maintenance needs a home, there has to be multi-annual funding for a platform to do this. Engaging with stakeholders to interpret these data is key.

- This was a very comprehensive discussion. It is the sum of the parts, everything has to arrive at the table at the same time to make the product work.

- What we haven't spoken about is the weighting of the various layers. This needs to be done in a room with the impacted groups, preferably with a large screen.

7. Closing remarks

The purpose of this document is to provide a summary of the feedback received during the EirWind Offshore Development Zones and Pathways interviews. This summary has been provided without commentary or analysis in order to provide a clear impartial snapshot of the nascent Irish offshore wind energy industry. It is hoped that this document can be used to facilitate informed discussions with key stakeholders relating to the future development of this sector.

It should be noted that the mapping phase of the interviews, summarised in Section 4 and Section 5, was a hypothetical exercise which used a rather crude GIS interface. In particular, development zone maps shown in Figure 18 and Figure 20 should be considered as being indicative only.

A content analysis, critical assessment of the development pathways along with a summary of opportunities and barriers to development will be presented in an accompanying report which will be completed in July 2020.

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to all participants for being so generous with their time during the interview process.